

Geneva's Press and Radio Microcosm and the League of Nations in the Interwar Period

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Introduction

How does the establishment of an international organization change the local media landscape of a small Swiss city, turning it into an international capital in a matter of months? In 1920, following skillful negotiations by Swiss diplomats at the 1919 Paris Peace Conference (Fleury 1981) in the wake of the First World War, the city of Geneva became the headquarters of the newly created League of Nations (LoN) (Bourneuf 2022). The first truly global parliament, which, despite its youthful mistakes, was to become the foundation of the multilateral system that still exists a century later through the United Nations agencies, the League was an institution that generated a great deal of media activity. On the one hand, because the press took a keen interest in the debates of its Assembly and Council, and in the worldly activity of its diplomats and heads of state, but also because the organization itself sought to spread its message throughout the world (Biltoft 2021) and set itself a mission of information (Seidenfaden 2024). More than internationalist ideals, what is at stake is the legitimacy of such an enterprise and its bureaucratic machinery (Seidenfaden 2020).

The local Geneva press was well placed to act as a sounding board for this new situation: Switzerland's neutrality during the Great War propelled several of its titles onto the international stage. The *Journal de Genève*, a liberal-conservative newspaper distinguished for decades by its high-quality international column, and the *Tribune de Genève* news daily, saw their circulations increase significantly during the conflict (Clavien 2017), and thus join the microcosm of foreign correspondents covering the activities of the League of Nations for the major Western media. This small cosmopolitan world formed a society where the porosity between journalists and the institutional communicators of the League's Information Section was significant. This gave rise to original media experiments, such as the creation of *Radio-Nations* in 1929, or a few minutes of daily news about the League on *Radio-Genève*. But it also resulted in dissident initiatives, such as the *Journal des Nations*, created in 1931 by anti-fascist journalists eager to defend the institution's ideals in the face of rising dictatorships (Cerutti 2006).

The "world center for information on international political affairs"

A question of infrastructure

The installation of an organization like the League of Nations required major infrastructural adaptations for the small city of Geneva. The development of its airport, of course, but also telephone connections with the major world capitals. At the end of the First World War, Geneva had only one direct telephone line, to Paris. Lines were gradually set up and, by 1925, the States agreed that telegrams to and from the League should have priority. In 1939, direct telephone lines to all European countries and dozens of non-European ones, attest to Geneva's infrastructural development during the interwar (Bourneuf 2022, 82–83). But the lack of means of communication in the early 1920s calls for more substantial investment, and in 1926 the creation of a radio telegraph station specifically dedicated to the League is proposed. It's not a new idea: as far back as 1919, when the founders met in Paris to discuss the location of the headquarters, the communications infrastructure was already an important issue. They probed the Swiss envoy about the possibility of setting up a radio station in Geneva, which posed a problem of sovereignty in neutral Helvetia. The U.S. government, still not out of the League of Nations project, was ready to move forward very quickly:

“In President Wilson's idea, it would be extremely important, for the development of the LoN and for the peaceful future of mankind, that Geneva should become, partly through this radiotelegraph station, the world center of information in international political matters”.¹

While this demonstrates that communication is an intrinsic need of modern diplomacy, this idea only truly took shape in 1930: Switzerland constructed the station, and the League of Nations financed the transmitters. Commissioned in 1932, the station served both radiophony and radiotelegraphy (fig. 1). It was therefore not merely a medium intended for the general public, but primarily a means of communication overseen by two sections of the institution: the Information Section and the Communications and Transit Section. In this perspective of an infrastructure at the service of the international organization, the main activity was therefore to receive and send telegrams to facilitate the work of diplomats and the secretariat. But it was quickly put to use for institutional communication. This technology also made it possible to collect live statistics from offices far from the headquarters: radiotelegraphy was used from the end of the 1920s to coordinate health efforts in Asia by collecting weekly epidemiological information at the Singapore office (*The League of Nations: A Pictorial Survey* 1929, 20). Even though the International Telegraph Union was still headquartered in the federal capital of Bern – it relocated to Geneva after the Second World War (Balbi and Fickers 2020) – Geneva truly became a prominent point on the global telecommunications map.

Figure 1. Undated photographs of the Radio-Nations station in Prangins. League of Nations Archives, UN Geneva, P132-01-007 / P285-01-142 / P285-01-066.

Establishing open diplomacy?

The establishment of such an institution in Geneva not only necessitated the development of infrastructure but also demanded a clear definition of how this new form of political organization interacts with the public and, crucially, with the messengers of information: the journalists. Although the secretariat worked continuously throughout the year, the visible face of the League was the General Assembly, an annual event that saw hundreds of national delegates and journalists crowding onto the shores of Lake Geneva. The meetings of the Council, the executive body bringing together the main powers, were also an important decision-making arena.

This quickly raised the question of public opinion and the openness of official sessions to the press. Two years after the first Assembly, the first point of the memorandum from the president of the

¹ Report by William Rappard to the Head of the Political Department, Felix Calonder, April 29, 1919, Diplomatic Documents of Switzerland 44114, p. 3. Cited by Fleury 1983, 197. Translated from French.

association of journalists accredited to the League of Nations reminded the organization that "it must be regarded as axiomatic that the League of Nations depends, not merely for its success but for its existence, on public opinion."² If, in 1922, it was still necessary to argue against private sessions, it is because the institution's initial good intentions clashed with the gradual return to a deeply rooted tradition of secret diplomacy, despite the negative experience of the Paris Peace Conference, criticized for drafting the Treaty of Versailles behind closed doors. Does the existence of an international organization truly depend on public opinion and journalists? In theory, it was established because the signatory parties believed it was justified. Yet, two years after its creation, it became apparent that the organization already needed to justify itself. Despite the grace period the League of Nations enjoyed in its early years, it found itself confronting the public opinions of the nations it represents. It was therefore crucial for the League to create a favorable environment for effective communication with its audiences. However, while the Assembly was regarded as a public meeting, the Council strongly opposed opening its sessions to external observers, as this naturally created pressure on negotiators. Instead, the League established a system of press releases, carefully reviewed and approved by the Council members, which were distributed to the media. And if, under pressure from journalists, some sessions became public, they were only accessible to a select group of privileged reporters. This forced the profession to adopt a form of collaboration, often among correspondents of the same country (Averbeck-Lietz 2024, 78). This selection clearly demonstrated that journalists were viewed as allies in the institution's communication strategy, rather than as independent actors free to cover all its activities. However, it was not for lack of communication: during the 1920s, the League of Nations published between 300 and 600 press releases per year! (*The League of Nations: A Pictorial Survey* 1929, 28).

Throughout its existence, the League of Nations continually debated the role of the press. It even convened conferences specifically dedicated to this issue (the first one in 1927). The topic repeatedly resurfaced –sometimes because journalists demanded broader access to deliberations, and at other times because the institution sought to combat "false and biased information" as part of its efforts toward "moral disarmament." This debate extended a few years later to radio broadcasting and culminated in 1936 with the signing of the *International Convention Concerning the Use of Broadcasting in the Cause of Peace* by 28 states (Tworek 2010, E. Seidenfaden 2019).

The transmedia microcosm

The ecosystem bringing together diplomats, international civil servants, and the media in Geneva during the interwar period constituted a highly distinctive microcosm (fig. 2). And it's not just about infrastructure, but about people and sociability. While the spatial dimensions of Geneva's internationalism have already been studied (Herren 2017), its specifically transmedia nature is what interests us here: the corridors of the Assembly where journalists waited for officials to exit, discussions at the press café, the telephone office where correspondents dictated their articles to their editorial teams, the bicycle couriers racing between the headquarters and journalists' residences, the members of the Information Section recording the speech of a statesman to broadcast it on the airwaves, the informal meetings with a national delegation in a hotel lounge or the formal press dinner that brought together the elite of the profession.

The evolution of a profession

First, it is interesting to note that all journalists accredited to the League of Nations were mentioned in the Official Journal when they attended an Assembly. They were listed there by nationality and with their address, which allows for a very interesting prosopography (Gellrich and Koenen 2024, 133). There were always around 200 to 350 journalists per Assembly between 1920 and 1938 (*The League of Nations: A Pictorial Survey* 1929, 28). A figure which, if we consider that they mostly wrote for several media, gives an idea of the extent of the media coverage of these events. The profiles are diverse, from official correspondents to independent journalists, including press agency employees, some of whom had permanent positions in Geneva, independently of the League of Nations

² Memorandum by Wilson Harris, January 8, 1922. League of Nations Archives, UN Geneva, Council Documents C.19.M.4.1922. Cited by Averbeck-Lietz 2024, 59.

Assemblies. Women were few in number, 5-10% in general, sometimes up to 25% in the British media (Gellrich and Koenen 2024, 138). With the development of radio, some naturally had a transmedia profile, either because they wrote indifferently for the press and the airwaves, or because they were, like Arthur Richard Burrows, recognized "voices" (first newsreader of the *BBC* in 1922 and from time to time registered as a journalist of the *Times* at the League of Nations, see Gellrich and Koenen 2024, 147). Moreover, other media professions also formed this community, in particular photographers – mostly local but also sometimes international – or press cartoonists (Reef 2019).

Figure 2. Schematic representation of Geneva's transmedia microcosm in the interwar period.

It is, however, unclear whether the local and international press collaborated beyond occasionally hiring a local journalist temporarily when a foreign publication lacked on-site staff. What is evident is that the cosmopolitan nature of this microcosm gave rise to local yet international initiatives, such as the *Journal des Nations* (1931), whose editor-in-chief, Carlo Emanuele A. Prato, was an Italian refugee and former correspondent for *The New York Times* (Cerutti 2002). This daily publication, which offered highly detailed coverage of international news and the League of Nations' diplomatic activities, represents a truly unique media phenomenon.

This environment also proved fertile for the institutionalization of the journalism profession. It is during this period that the *Fédération Internationale des Journalistes* was established in Paris in 1926, owing much of its legitimacy to the League, as it immediately became its principal interlocutor during the 1927 Press Experts Conference (Beyersdorf 2016). Also noteworthy are the Association of Journalists Accredited to the League and the work of the International Labour Organization, which began investigating the status and working conditions of journalists as early as 1925. All these initiatives highlight the "co-evolution" of journalism and the public relations strategies of international organizations (Koenen, Averbek-Lietz, and Gellrich 2024, 9).

The symbiosis of this ecosystem of journalism and public relations is also evident in the Information Section's intense activity in keeping abreast of what's being published about the institution. Before it outsourced this work, it employed professional readers who read 200 press titles every day and distributed the thousands of clippings to the relevant sections (Gellrich 2023). It then employed the Geneva-based company *Argus Suisse*, which specialized in this work, delivering tens, if not hundreds, of thousands of press clippings a year (Averbek-Lietz 2024, 109), a mandate that represented a very substantial budget for the section.

Mobility and blurred lines

It goes without saying that the majority of the staff in the League of Nations' Information Section previously worked as journalists, highlighting a structural mobility between these two worlds. For example, this was the case for the section's director, Pierre Comert, a former French journalist and German literature professor in Göttingen, who, from 1916, served as press attaché at the French Embassy in London (the backbone of the Secretariat was assembled while the League was being prepared in London in 1919–1920). This was also true for dozens of others, such as Max Beer, a journalist for the *Kölnische Zeitung* accredited to the League between 1920 and 1927. On the recommendation of Gustav Stresemann himself, Beer joined the Information Section when Germany was moving closer to the organization. There, he organized the 1927 Press Experts Conference. He left the League in 1930 to return to journalism, first in Germany and later in exile in France and Switzerland. After World War II, he was hired by the Public Information Department of the United Nations (Averbeck-Lietz 2024, 82).

It was not uncommon for precarious working conditions, the habit of acting as correspondents for multiple media outlets, and the lack of clear rules to create situations that blurred the line between communication and journalism. For instance, this was the case with Vernon Bartlett, head of the London Branch Office of the Information Section, who later moved on to the *BBC* but reportedly wrote articles for *The Times* during his tenure. The most emblematic case is that of Arthur Sweetser, whose actions prompted the Secretariat to clarify that its members were not permitted to publish articles in a personal capacity (Averbeck-Lietz 2024, 85). Often, this was because the novelty of the institution meant that the distinction between journalism and institutional communication was still being defined, partly due to the back-and-forth nature of these actors' careers and their highly personal assessment of the situation (in several instances, their writing for the press and radio was done in good faith to compensate for the lack of media coverage of certain League of Nations activities!). Moreover, this politico-media microcosm was, unsurprisingly, not immune to intertwined personal situations, such as that of Antonina Vallentin. A journalist of Polish origin initially working for Stresemann's German Foreign Ministry, she covered the League of Nations between 1926 and 1928 before marrying Julien Luchaire, the director of the newly created International Institute of Intellectual Cooperation of the League of Nations. Luchaire's son Jean was also a journalist at this time and occasionally covered the League while his father was still working there, in a way taking over his father's new wife (Gellrich and Koenen 2024, 159). But while his father, Julien, fully embraced the internationalist vision by seeking to strengthen France's position in cultural diplomacy (Grandjean 2022), Jean Luchaire pursued a career increasingly at odds with the values of the League of Nations. He later became involved in nationalist press and, from 1940, openly collaborationist, ultimately serving as the chief censor of the French press and a propagandist for Vichy, while his father joined the Resistance. This personal episode highlights that the transmedia microcosm of "International Geneva" was nevertheless composed of actors from across the political spectrum, including Italian fascists and German journalists controlled by the regime from 1933 onward.

Taking advantage of new media: radio and film & the League of Nations

While this paper cannot focus on all the communication activities of the Information Section, which is an object of renewed interest in recent years (see Löhr and Herren 2014, Seidenfaden 2022 or Van Dijk 2022), it is interesting to see how it attempted to take advantage of the telecommunication infrastructure described above and how it intersected with the traditional media of the time, the press.

When the local and international press were invited to visit *Radio-Nations'* brand-new facilities in early March 1932, the *Journal de Genève* concluded that it was “an admirable and useful work”³, because it also served the press. In fact, *Radio-Nations* was in no way in competition with the print media, since it limited itself to a weekly broadcast, late on Sunday evenings, in French, English and Spanish. From 1937 onwards, it also transmitted reports on the work of the Assembly. It was also used to broadcast concerts by the Orchestre de la Suisse Romande around the world. And, in the reverse scenario, was

³ "Les stations émettrice et réceptrice de Radio-Nations", *Journal de Genève*, 2 March 1932, p. 4. Available on the Impresso app: <https://impresso-project.ch/app/issue/JDG-1932-03-02-a/page/JDG-1932-03-02-a-p0004>

paid for by major American radio stations to broadcast some of their content to Europe. But basically, technological change has had little effect on the type of communication practiced by the League, which has always relied, as in its more traditional communiqués, on a precise and elitist expert discourse that “overestimated the public's powers of rationality” in the era of the emergence of mass-based politics based on new media (Akami 2019, 167).

Although the audio recordings have not been preserved, the annual reports list the topics of these approximately 45-minute broadcasts: speeches by Secretary-General Eric Drummond, discussions with the President of the Assembly, interviews of the Secretariat conducted by local or international journalists, responses to listener letters, lectures by experts on technical achievements of the League, reports from the Secretariat on specific actions, and more.⁴ Despite its remarkable regularity – broadcasting weekly in its early years and increasing its pace to 748 official programs between 1936 and 1938 (Bourneuf 2022) – the overall volume of broadcasts was not very significant compared to radio stations that aired programs throughout the day. What truly sets *Radio-Nations* apart is its global ambition. At the time, it was the only station broadcasting simultaneously worldwide (the Vatican station had a similar ambition but lacked sufficiently powerful transmitters). In its first year, while only 49 programs were broadcast, the audience was estimated at 100,000 listeners, from whom they received 8,797 letters in Geneva. Additionally, 150 press articles reproduced the content of their broadcasts, and 8 other radio stations relayed their programs.⁵

Figure 3. Left: *Le Radio* 11 March 1932, A full-page spread detailing the first live broadcast of an entire League of Nations assembly, the extraordinary session devoted to the Sino-Japanese War (p.348). Right: *Le Radio* 23 September 1932, A half-page of press cartoons allowing readers/listeners to put a face to the voices they hear on the radio (top, p.1231) and an extract from the week's program, where we see the space reserved for Suès' chronicle (bottom, p.1224).

On a much more local scale, Radio-Genève also showed significant interest in the work of the League of Nations. Here too, very few archives of their broadcasts on the League remain – at most, a few dozen recordings, primarily major speeches by heads of state preserved for their potential future

⁴ "Premier rapport annuel sur le service de la section d'information", 1933, League of Nations Archives, UN Geneva, R4325-9G-14701-742, p. 1-3.

⁵ Idem, p. 4 and 12.

reuse, along with more comprehensive coverage of the League's final session in 1946. However, the weekly magazine of the Société romande de radiodiffusion, *Le Radio*, helps partially fill this gap (fig. 3): during League sessions, the Geneva station dedicated 10 to 15 minutes daily to the "Travaux de la Société des Nations" at 8:00 p.m., hosted by Marcel-William Suès, a pioneer of news broadcasting in French-speaking Switzerland (Musy 1984).

Regarding cinema – the other future mass-media of the interwar period – the League of Nations was a latecomer (Dijk 2023). Prompted by Mussolini's Italy, which sought to counterbalance French initiatives related to intellectual cooperation (Grandjean 2018, 371–78) and aimed to assert its influence in the cultural diplomacy of the late 1920s, the League founded the *International Educational Cinematographic Institute* in Rome in 1928 (Faillibert 2020, Wilke 2024). However, this institute functioned more as a center for reflection on the use of film rather than a site of production. The League of Nations nevertheless ventured into "film-splaining" its activities (Jensen, Schulz, and Seidenfaden 2019) in 1935 through an "infomercial" titled *The League of Nations at Work* (fig. 4). While this document is highly valuable for understanding the organization's communication strategy, its distribution remains more challenging to trace.

Figure 4. Screenshot from a scene in the film "League of Nations at Work" showing the telegraph office at the League of Nations headquarters, accompanied by a description of the scenes.⁶

Making the world smaller

The infrastructure established in Geneva helped reduce the reaction time of the political world. The Sino-Japanese conflict, often regarded as the final nail in the coffin of the League of Nations' ability to resolve international disputes, paradoxically serves as the perfect example of its effectiveness in circulating information. In March 1932, during the very early days of *Radio-Nations*, the live broadcast of an entire extraordinary assembly – rather than simply the delayed dissemination of a few key speeches – was widely praised (fig. 3). However, the most striking demonstration came a year later, in February 1933, when the League finally released its report accusing Japan of invading Manchuria. This marked a major achievement for the organization: Thanks to its transmission network, the 15,000-word report was sent to all corners of the globe and reproduced in full in media worldwide (fig. 5), including Chinese newspapers, just 24 hours later (Bourneuf 2022, 85). In addition to this telegram – which, in total, required several kilometers of tape – *Radio-Nations* also used its regular broadcast to explain the report.

⁶ Part 1 can be seen here: <https://media.un.org/avlibrary/en/asset/d211/d2113114> (UN Audiovisual Library).

COUZENS BANK BILL SWIFTLY MADE LAW; NEW RELIEF LOANS

Carry to Settle Republican Leaders' Row: Macy and Knevez at Odds on Tax Post

STATE LIQUOR BOARD NORRIS LEADS MOVE DISAGREES ON PLANS FOR BIPARTY UNION FOR VOTE ON REPEAL OF 'PROGRESSIVES'

CHAOYANG FALLS AS JAPANESE ADVANCE; FOUR ARMIES AND AIR FLEET IN DRIVE; WASHINGTON APPROVES LEAGUE'S ACTION

Radio Aerials of the League of Nations Near Geneva. From Which the 15,000-Word Report of the Sino-Japanese Situation Was Recently Broadcast Around the World.

Broadcast of Manchurian Report Proved Value of "Radio-Nations" at Geneva

THE earliest plans for the League of Nations in the burst of enthusiasm for the League immediately after the World War included a radio station with power sufficient to stridle the earth.

The efficiency of the station and the value for quick and complete dissemination of information were strikingly illustrated recently when the League's 15,000-word report on the Sino-Japanese dispute in Manchuria was broadcast to the entire world. The New York Times wireless station copied the dots and dashes of the report in ten hours direct from Geneva and it was printed in full in *The Times* on the following morning.

Though the subject was under discussion for many years, it was only in September, 1929, that the Assembly of the League of Nations resolved to erect a wireless station which would issue independent and direct communications between the League and the greatest possible number of its member States.

"We can hardly estimate the change that may be made in international relations," remarked Sir Eric Drummond, Secretary General of the League, "if people in various parts of the world become accustomed not only to the thought but even to the actual voices of the League of Nations in the League of Nations."

The aerial system consists of three groups of beam aerials. The first group (Marconi system) comprises two parts, one of which is directed toward South America, the other toward the Far East, each side being composed of two complete sets of aerials one for day and one for night working.

The second aerial group (Telefunken system) is directed toward Central America and can be shifted in the direction of Australia and the West Indies. This group is also divided into a night and day array. The third aerial is directed toward South America and can be shifted toward British India. This aerial has been designed for one wavelength only.

Apart from these three groups of beam aerials the station possesses three semi-directional aerials. The two short-wave transmitters have an aerial power of twenty kilowatts, sufficient for reaching the most distant parts of the globe.

The medium wave transmitter of fifty-kilowatt aerial power can work on waves between 2,000 and 5,000 meters, and it is possible to establish by means of it communications with any point in Europe. New York hears the 20.64-meter wavelength twice there is a band of daylight between Switzerland and the United States. Soon after 2 P. M. in New York, a stronger sig-

League's Note and Reply

70,000 MEN IN OFFENSIVE

Bombs Do Much Damage to the Chinese Defense at Lingyuan Pass.

TWO MORE ARMIES START

Japan Hurts Big New Forces Into Joint as Chinese Regulars Prepare to Fight.

PHIRING AT SHANHAIKWAN

Advance Proceeding Through Blizzards From Gobi in 12 Baby Zens Temperatures.

BY HALEY'S ARMY

News from the New York Times, SHANHAIKWAN, Feb. 25.—Chongqing, the second largest city of China, was shelled by Japanese planes today. The report of this city, about 1,000 miles from the Manchurian border, where a huge Chinese force has been ordered to meet the Japanese advance, is the first of a series of reports from the Chinese front which indicate that the Japanese are making rapid progress. The Japanese have captured the city of Chongqing, and are now advancing toward the city of Kailashan, about 100 miles from Chongqing. The Japanese have also captured the city of Kailashan, and are now advancing toward the city of Kailashan. The Japanese have also captured the city of Kailashan, and are now advancing toward the city of Kailashan.

REPLY OF MR. STIMSON.

There has been considerable discussion in the United States in the past few days regarding the League of Nations and its action in the Sino-Japanese dispute. It is the policy of the United States to support the League of Nations in its efforts to maintain peace and order in the world. The United States is committed to the League of Nations and will continue to support its efforts to resolve international disputes. The United States is committed to the League of Nations and will continue to support its efforts to resolve international disputes.

Figure 5. "Broadcast of Manchurian Report Proved Value of "Radio-Nations" at Geneva", New York Times, 26 February 1933, p.X10. The technical feat is celebrated with a photograph of the Prangins station.

Next steps

While the inventory of communication tools is now well-established in recent scholarship, one question remains unresolved: what is the real impact of public relations strategies on the transmedia microcosm and its outputs, and subsequently on international public opinion (assuming the notion of public opinion even holds meaningful weight in a world still heavily compartmentalized along national lines)? Conversely, what is the effect of these processes of mediatization on the political institution itself?

For instance, did media innovations lead to changes in how delegates addressed the plenary sessions of the Assembly? The near-total absence of radio archives from this period makes an exhaustive analysis of the media productions challenging. However, the goal of this research is to lay the groundwork for a study of the content of the Geneva press, in an effort to measure the precise media coverage of this international organization in this very specific local context.

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